

HORIZON2020 European Center of Excellence

Deliverable D6.2
Webpage with education resources from MaX

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D6.2: Webpage with education resources from MaX

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1. Executive Summary

Scope of the **WP6 Training & education: Addressing the skills gap** is to address the skills gaps that are relevant to support HPC applications in materials, both on the shorter- and on the medium/longer-term perspective. In order to do so, the CoE planned to structure a specific section in the CoE portal (<http://www.max-centre.eu>), so to allow users access to the available training and education offer and learning materials. This intends to include activities offered by both the consortium and external institutions, to maintain an updated map of the existing initiatives in training and education and of the emerging needs in view of future roadmap and initiatives. All instruments are being developed in close connection with other CoE's, PRACE, Quantum ESPRESSO Foundation etc.

This document is the deliverable D6.2 of the MaX project and briefly describes the **Webpage with education resources developed on the MaX website**. The related staff developed of a specific section of the CoE portal dedicated to Education and Training, allowing users access to the available offer and learning materials. (month 12)

This is a living document and will be updated continuously in the course of the project.

2. Training and education webpages

2.1 Structure

The access point on the MaX portal is deliberately simple and plain in order to be as much user-friendly as possible. The structure is the following:

A main page **“Training and education”** is linked under **“Services”** (button on the main bar), the path is [Home](#) > training and education and the specific address is <http://www.max-centre.eu/training-and-education/>

From the “**Training and education**” page it is possible to access different pages that correspond to the foreseen sections of the training activities:

- Workshops and schools
- Training material related to the MaX flagship codes
- Open Online courses and videolectures
- Training through research in the CoE labs

2.2 “Training and education” page

[Home](#) > training and education

It is the access page to the training services. It offers an overview of the CoE involvement in the topic.

The screenshot shows the website www.max-centre.eu/training-and-education/. The page features the MaX logo with the tagline "DRIVING THE EXASCALE TRANSITION". A navigation menu includes links for "the centre", "materials design", "services", "people", "events", "news", "links", "open position", "contact", "user portal", and "intranet". The main content area is titled "training and education" and includes a sub-header "Home - training and education". A text block states: "MaX offers **integrated** training and education in the field of HPC developments and in the **computational materials science domain**. Our offer includes specific **workshops and schools** on HPC applications in computational material sciences, **University courses and materials** at both undergraduate and graduate level, and the possibility of **training through research in the CoE labs**. Specific training activities for industrial end-users are offered as a dedicated service. **Contributing to a community effort to bridge the skills gap is a major commitment of MaX.**" Below this text is a list of training activities: "Workshops and schools", "Training material related to the MaX flagship codes", "Open Online courses and videolectures", and "Training through research in the CoE labs". On the right side, there is a section titled "Upcoming Events" listing three events: "Developer workshop on new programming paradigms" (August 29 @ 8:00 am - 5:00 pm), "CECAM/Psi-k/CCP9 Graduate School" (September 5 - September 9), and "School on Parallel Programming and Parallel Architecture for HPC" (October 3 - October 14). A "View All Events" link is provided at the bottom of this section.

2.3 “Workshops and schools” page

[Home](#) > [training and education](#) > list of workshops & schools

In this page the events organized by the MaX consortium are listed in a table, organized in past and upcoming events. All events are linked to specific posts that are also visible from the list “Events” (button on the mainbar). All events are also visible in the right column.

In the “Workshop & schools” page we put all relevant training events. Events flagged with the small MaX logo are organized or supported directly by the MaX CoE staff.

Home > [training and education](#) > list of workshops & schools

list of workshops & schools

A list of training events (schools and workshops) is given below. Events flagged with the Max logo are organized or supported directly by the MaX CoE.

UPCOMING EVENTS

TITLE	SITE	PERSON IN CHARGE	DATE
CECAM/Psi-k/CCP9 Graduate School [info]	CECAM-UK-HARTREE (UK)		5-9/9/2016
School on Parallel Programming and Parallel Architecture for HPC [info]	Trieste (IT)	I. Giroto	3-14/10/2016
Advanced Workshop on High-Performance & High-Throughput Materials Simulations using QUANTUM ESPRESSO [info]	Trieste (IT)	N. Marzari	16-28/01/2017
Prace-MaX training event [info]	Bologna (IT)	C. Cavazzoni	TBA (Dec. 2016)
Developer workshop on new programming paradigms [info]	Barcelona (ES)		TBA

All links [\[info\]](#) address to specific event’s page where all relevant information is stored: dates, location, links to map, website, etc.

2.4 “Training material related to the MaX flagship codes” page

[Home](#) > [training and education](#) > training material related to the MaX flagship codes

This is a very useful pages with links to courses focussed on the MaX flagship codes. All linked materials are free and can be used by interested researchers. As all the other pages, this one is continuously updated.

[Home](#) > [training and education](#) > training material related to the MaX flagship codes

training material related to the MaX flagship codes

	Electronic structure calculations using plane waves Lecture notes and tutorials: http://www.quantum-espresso.org/tutorials/
	Efficient density-functional calculations with atomic orbitals Lecture notes and tutorials: http://departments.icmab.es/leem/siesta/Documentation/Tutorials/index.html
	Full Potential Linearized Augmented Plane Wave Method: A DFT all-electron method Lecture notes: http://juser.fz-juelich.de/record/151915/files/Schlusseltech_74.pdf
	Many Body Perturbation Theory Lecture notes on MBPT theoretical background, Quasi particle correction (GW) and absorption spectroscopy (TDDFT and BSE): http://www.yambo-code.org/theory/lectures.php Tutorial on the use of the Yambo code: http://www.yambo-code.org/tutorials/index.php
	Path Integral techniques for the atomic-scale modelling of the quantum behavior of materials and molecules. (i-PI) Tutorial: http://epfl-cosmo.github.io/gle4md/index.html?page=ipi&psub=tutorial Lecture Slides: https://www.cecami.org/workshop-5-1314.html
	Automated Interactive Infrastructure and Database for Computational Science http://www.aiida.net/?page_id=591

2.5 “Open online courses and videolectures” page

[Home](#) > [training and education](#) > open online courses and videolectures

At the moment this page is simply a placeholder. Courses and lectures are under preparation and will be accessible through this page.

[Home](#) > [training and education](#) > open online courses and videolectures

open online courses and videolectures

One of the featured tasks of MaX is to offer to students and researchers a certain amount of online courses and videolectures in order to favour training at distance.

Such materials are yet under preparation and will be made available asap in this dedicated page.

Upcoming Events

CECAM/Psi-k/CCP9 Graduate School

September 5 - September 9

School on Parallel Programming and Parallel Architecture for HPC

October 3 - October 14

2.6 “Training through research in the CoE labs” page

[Home](#) > [training and education](#) > training through research in the CoE labs

This page provides information about the specific tailor-made training that is possible to receive in CoE labs.

Stories of training and trained researchers will be given in the same page as soon as possible.

[Home](#) > [training and education](#) > training through research in the CoE labs

training through research in the CoE labs

MaX offers **specific training** by hosting in its labs industrial researchers, academic researchers and PhD students interested in the computational tools developed in the CoE.

MaX also offers internships of short/medium duration to PhD students willing to gain experience with the MaX flagship codes.

- Interested users can contact the Center at info@max-centre.eu (see [Contacts](#)) specifying the keywords they are interested in (e.g., node, code, specific topics).

Tailor-made training periods and courses will be developed for them.

Upcoming Events

CECAM/Psi-k/CCP9 Graduate School

September 5 - September 9

School on Parallel Programming and Parallel Architecture for HPC

October 3 - October 14

PRACE-MaX training

December 15 @ 8:00 am - 5:00 pm

[View All Events](#)